

A P O L L O

D6.3: 2nd APOLLO TRAINING MATERIAL

WP6 – Pilot operation and evaluation

Authors: DragutinProtic, Milan Kilibarda, BranislavBajat, Ivan Aleksic

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 687412.

Disclaimer

Any dissemination of results reflects only the author's view and the European Commission is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains.

Copyright message

© APOLLO Consortium, 2016

This deliverable contains original unpublished work except where clearly indicated otherwise. Acknowledgement of previously published material and of the work of others has been made through appropriate citation, quotation or both. Reproduction is authorised provided the source is acknowledged.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 687412.

Document Information

Grant Agreement Number	687412	Acronym	APOLLO	
Full Title	Advisory platform for small farms based on earth observation			
Horizon 2020 Call	EO-1-2015: Bringing EO applications to the market			
Type of Action	Innovation Action			
Start Date	1 st May 2016	Duration	34 months	
Project URL	http:// APOLLO -h2020.eu/			
Document URL	-			
EU Project Officer	Iulia Simion			
Project Coordinator	PolimachiSimeonidou			
Deliverable	D6.3: 2 nd APOLLO Training Material			
Work Package	WP6 – Pilot operation and evaluation			
Date of Delivery	Contractual	M18	Actual	M18
Nature	DEC	Dissemination Level	PU	
Lead Beneficiary	DRAXIS Environmental SA			
Lead Author	DragutinProtic	email	protic@grf.bg.ac.rs	
	UBFCE			
Other authors	Milan Kilibarda, BranislavBajat, Ivan Aleksic, Stelios Kotsopoulos			
Reviewer(s)				
Keywords	Training material			

Document History

Version	Issue Date	Stage	Changes	Contributor
0.1	30/06/2018	Draft	Draft version intended to serve the users during the pilot phase, User Guides updated and translated to pilot languages	UBFCE
0.2	20/02/2019	Final	User Guides updated. Video tutorials created.	UBFCE

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 687412.

Table of Contents

Executive summary	5
Introduction	5
1 Content of the training material	6
Appendix I: User Guide	7

Executive summary

This document reports on the development of the first set of **APOLLO** training material within the context of the Task 6.2 Pilot training and execution. The current set of training material follow up the first version of the training material published as deliverable D6.2 and reflects the functionalities of **APOLLO** platform version after alpha and beta phase and supports execution of the pilots. The material was being updated to the end of the project according the and is ready for the operational exploitation of **APOLLO** platform.

Introduction

One of the main objectives in **APOLLO** project is to offer high quality services to farmers that will help them increase their productivity. The offerings can be summarized in 6 different services i) Tillage scheduling, ii) Irrigation scheduling, iii) Crop growth monitoring, iv) Crop yield estimation, v) Weather forecasting (additional service) and vi) Management zones (additional service). Crop biomass is one of the biophysical parameters of crops that will be produced to support two of the services, namely crop growth monitoring and crop yield estimation. The services will be tested in three pilot areas: La Mancha (Spain), Pella (Greece) and Ruma (Serbia).

This deliverable consists of a set of User Guides and video tutorial and it is aimed to support the end-users in using the **APOLLO** platform in pilot phase. The training material reflects the currently developed functionalities of **APOLLO**.

1 Content of the training material

The current version of the **APOLLO** Training Material consists of:

- User Guide v2.2 (Appendix I)
 - Getting started
 - How to register...
 - How to log in ...
 - How to edit profile settings...
 - How to add parcels...
 - How to use the services...

The User Guide is released in English, Spanish, Greek and Serbian

- Video Tutorials
 - Login and profile settings video tutorial
<https://drive.google.com/file/d/1bebzSnNwr23krucavy-FwnbRGt0UIV8a/view?usp=sharing>
 - Adding new parcel https://drive.google.com/file/d/1nGoSGfkXVfbCXnUuQ-_2SxS-fKr9ENSP/view?usp=sharing
 - Using **APOLLO** services
<https://drive.google.com/file/d/18gCLeNFQkMATYL4Oyrs8dYP7KYbdEj5e/view?usp=sharing>

Appendix I: User Guide

Get started with APOLLO services

Open APOLLO platform in your web browser (Chrome, Mozilla...). The address is: <http://apollo.draxis.gr> and follow the steps:

1st STEP
REGISTER AN APOLLO ACCOUNT

2nd STEP
LOG IN TO YOUR APOLLO ACCOUNT AND SET UP YOUR PROFILE

3rd STEP
ADD YOUR FIELDS

4th STEP
USE APOLLO SERVICES

- Tillage Scheduling
- Irrigation Scheduling
- Crop Yield Estimation
- Crop Growth Monitoring

APOLLO

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 687412.

Empieza a usar los servicios APOLLO

Abre la plataforma APOLLO en tu navegador (Chrome o Mozilla).

La dirección es: <http://apollo.draxis.gr> Y sigue los pasos:

A P O L L O

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 687412.

Započnite vaše APOLLO usluge

Otvorite APOLLO platformu u vašem internet pretraživaču (Chrome, Mozilla...). Adresa je: <http://apollo.draxis.gr> I pratite korake

A P O L L O

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 687412.

HOW TO REGISTER AN APOLLO ACCOUNT...

Open **APOLLO** platform in your web browser (Chrome, Mozilla...). The address is: <http://APOLLO.draxis.gr>

Click on REGISTER pane

Fill in the requested information (e-mail, Name, Last name, password) and then click on REGISTER

A screenshot of a web browser window showing a registration form for 'Apollo'. The browser address bar shows 'apollo.draxis.gr/register'. The form fields are: 'EMAIL ADDRESS' with 'farmerapollo@gmail.com', 'NAME' with 'Apollo', 'LAST NAME' with 'Farmer', 'PASSWORD' with '.....', and 'CONFIRM PASSWORD' with '.....'. A green 'REGISTER' button is highlighted with a red box at the bottom of the form.

You received the Account Activation e-mail. Go to your e-mail account and open the e-mail received from **APOLLO**. Click on **VERIFY YOUR EMAIL**

New tab in your browser is opened. Click on here to complete your registration.

CÓMO REGISTRARSE EN LA PLATAFORMA APOLLO...

Acceda a la plataforma **APOLLO** en su buscador (Chrome o Mozilla).

La dirección es: <http://APOLLO.draxis.gr>

Pulse sobre el botón “REGISTRO”(REGISTER).

The screenshot shows a web browser window with the URL apollo.draxis.gr/login. The page features the APOLLO logo at the top center. Below the logo is the heading "Login". The main content is a white login form with the following elements:

- EMAIL ADDRESS:** A text input field with the placeholder "Your email address".
- PASSWORD:** A text input field with the placeholder "Your password".
- REMEMBER ME:** A checkbox next to the text "REMEMBER ME".
- Forgot your password?:** A green link text.
- LOG IN:** A green button.

Below the login form, there is a link "Dont have an account?" with a "REGISTER" button next to it. The "REGISTER" button is highlighted with a red rectangular box.

Rellene la información requerida (dirección e-mail, nombre, apellidos, password) y después pulse sobre “REGISTRO” (*REGISTER*).

The screenshot shows a web browser window with the URL `apollo.draxis.gr/register`. The page title is "APOLLO" and the main heading is "Register". The form contains the following fields:

- EMAIL ADDRESS: `farmerspain@gmail.com`
- NAME: `Farmer`
- LAST NAME: `Spain`
- PASSWORD: `.....`
- CONFIRM PASSWORD: `.....`

At the bottom of the form is a green button labeled "REGISTER". Below the form, there is a link "Already have an account?" and a "LOG IN" button.

Recibirá un e-mail de Activación de Cuenta. Vaya a su cuenta de correo electrónico y abra el e-mail recibido desde **APOLLO**. Pulse sobre “VERIFIQUE SU CORREO ELECTRÓNICO”.

Se abrirá una nueva pestaña en su navegador. Pulse sobre "here" para completar su registro.

ΠΩΣ ΝΑ ΔΗΜΙΟΥΡΓΗΣΕΤΕ ΕΝΑΝ ΛΟΓΑΡΙΑΣΜΟ APOLLO...

Ανοίξτε την πλατφόρμα **APOLLO** στο πρόγραμμα περιήγησης ιστού (Chrome, Mozilla ...). Η διεύθυνση είναι: <http://APOLLO.draxis.gr>

Κάντε κλικ στο παράθυρο Εγγραφή

APOLLO

Σύνδεση

EMAIL
Your email address

ΚΩΔΙΚΟΣ ΠΡΟΒΑΣΗΣ
Your password

ΝΑ ΜΕ ΘΥΜΑΣΤΑΙ [Ξεχάσατε τον κωδικό πρόσβασης;](#)

ΣΥΝΔΕΣΗ

Δεν έχετε λογαριασμό; **Εγγραφή**

Συμπληρώστε τις πληροφορίες που ζητούνται (e-mail, Όνομα, Επώνυμο, κωδικός πρόσβασης) και στη συνέχεια κάντε κλικ στο ΕΓΓΡΑΦΗ

Λάβατε το μήνυμα ηλεκτρονικού ταχυδρομείου ενεργοποίησης λογαριασμού. Μεταβείτε στο λογαριασμό ηλεκτρονικού ταχυδρομείου σας και ανοίξτε το e-mail που λάβατε από το **APOLLO**. Κάντε κλικ στην **ΕΠΑΛΗΘΕΥΣΗ ΤΟΥ EMAIL ΣΑΣ**

Η νέα καρτέλα στο πρόγραμμα περιήγησής σας ανοίγει. Κάντε κλικ [εδώ](#) για να ολοκληρώσετε την εγγραφή σας.

KAKO DA REGISTRUJETE SVOJ APOLLO NALOG...

Otvorite **APOLLO** platformu u vašem internet pretraživaču (Chrome, Mozilla...). Adresa je: <http://APOLLO.draxis.gr>

Kliknite na prozor za REGISTRACIJU

Popunite tražene informacije (e-mail, Ime, Prezime, lozinka) i onda kliknite na REGISTRUJ SE

The screenshot shows a web browser window with the URL `apollo.draxis.gr/register`. The form contains the following fields:

- EMAIL ADDRESS: `farmerapollo@gmail.com`
- NAME: `Apollo`
- LAST NAME: `Farmer`
- PASSWORD: `.....`
- CONFIRM PASSWORD: `.....`

A green button labeled "REGISTER" is highlighted with a red box at the bottom of the form.

Primili ste e-mail za aktivaciju naloga. Idite na vaš e-mail nalog, otvorite e-mail koji ste primili od **APOLLO**. Kliknite na VERIFIKUJTE VAŠ MEJL

Novi prozor u vašem pretraživaču je otvoren. Kliknite na **ovde** (**here**) da biste završili registraciju.

HOW TO LOG IN YOUR APOLLO ACCOUNT...

Insert the e-mail address and password that were set during registration

Click on LOG IN

You are logged in your **APOLLO** account. Your **APOLLO** dashboard is now open.

CÓMO INICIAR SESIÓN EN SU CUENTA APOLLO...

Escriba la dirección de e-mail y la contraseña con las que se registró.

The screenshot shows a web browser window with the URL `apollo.draxis.gr/login?confirmed=true`. The page title is "Log in" and features the "APOLLO" logo. The login form contains the following fields and elements:

- EMAIL ADDRESS:** `farmerapollo@gmail.com`
- PASSWORD:** A field containing seven asterisks (`*****`), which is highlighted with a red rectangular box.
- REMEMBER ME:** An unchecked checkbox.
- Forgot password?:** A link in green text.
- LOG IN:** A green button at the bottom of the form.

Haga click sobre “INICIAR SESIÓN” (LOG IN).

Usted ha iniciado sesión en su cuenta **APOLLO**. Su pantalla de control **APOLLO** está ahora abierta.

ΠΩΣ ΝΑ ΣΥΝΔΕΘΕΙΤΕ ΣΤΟΝ ΛΟΓΑΡΙΑΣΜΟ ΣΑΣ APOLLO...

Εισάγετε τη διεύθυνση ηλεκτρονικού ταχυδρομείου και τον κωδικό πρόσβασης που καθορίστηκαν κατά την εγγραφή

APOLLO

Σύνδεση

EMAIL
farmerapollo@gmail.com

ΚΩΔΙΚΟΣ ΠΡΟΣΒΑΣΗΣ

ΝΑ ΜΕ ΘΥΜΑΣΑΙ [Ξεχάσατε τον κωδικό πρόσβασης;](#)

ΣΥΝΔΕΣΗ

Δεν έχετε λογαριασμό; [Εγγραφή](#)

Κάντε κλικ στο ΣΥΝΔΕΣΗ

APOLLO

Σύνδεση

EMAIL
farmerapollo@gmail.com

ΚΩΔΙΚΟΣ ΠΡΟΒΑΣΗΣ

ΝΑ ΜΕ ΘΥΜΑΣΑΙ [Ξεχάσατε τον κωδικό πρόσβασης;](#)

ΣΥΝΔΕΣΗ

Δεν έχετε λογαριασμό; [Εγγραφή](#)

Είστε συνδεδεμένοι στο λογαριασμό σας **APOLLO**. Ο πίνακας εργαλείων **APOLLO** είναι πλέον ανοιχτός.

APOLLO ΑΡΧΙΚΗ ΟΘΟΝΗ ΦΟΡΟΥΜ ΧΡΗΣΤΗΣ APOLLO

Αρχική οθόνη

+ Εισαγωγή Νέου Χωραφίου

0 ΧΩΡΑΦΙΑ 0 ΕΙΔΟΠΟΙΗΣΕΙΣ ΟΡΓΩΜΑΤΟΣ 0 ΕΙΔΟΠΟΙΗΣΕΙΣ ΠΟΤΙΣΜΑΤΟΣ 0 ΕΙΔΟΠΟΙΗΣΕΙΣ ΠΡΟΒΛΕΨΗΣ ΣΥΓΚΟΜΙΔΗΣ

Τύπος Καλλιέργειας # Χωραφίων Εκτάρια Περιοχής Υπηρεσίες

ΤΟ ΤΡΕΧΟΝ ΠΑΚΕΤΟ ΣΥΝΔΡΟΜΗΣ ΣΑΣ ΕΙΝΑΙ ΑΣΗΜΕΝΟ
Χρειάζεστε περισσότερα; Αναβαθμίστε το πακέτο της συνδρομής σας Apollo Gold για να έχετε απεριόριστο αριθμό πελατών, χωραφίων, τύπων καλλιεργειών και άλλα.

ΕΠΙΚΟΙΝΩΗΣΤΕ

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 687412.

KAKO DA SE ULOGUJETE NA VAŠ APOLLO NALOG...

Unesite e-mail adresu i lozinku koje su podešene u toku registracije

The screenshot shows a web browser window with the URL `apollo.draxis.gr/login?confirmed=true`. The page features the Apollo logo at the top center. Below the logo, the heading "Log in" is displayed. The login form is centered and includes the following elements:

- EMAIL ADDRESS:** A text input field containing the email address `farmerapollo@gmail.com`.
- PASSWORD:** A text input field containing masked characters (`*****`), highlighted with a red rectangular box.
- REMEMBER ME:** A checkbox that is currently unchecked.
- Forgot password?:** A green text link located to the right of the "REMEMBER ME" checkbox.
- LOG IN:** A prominent green button at the bottom of the form.

Kliknite na dugme ULOGUJ SE

Sada ste ulogovani na vaš **APOLLO** nalog. Vaša **APOLLO** komandna tabla je sada otvorena.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 687412.

Promenite jezik na padajućem meniju

The screenshot shows the Apollo Farmer web application interface. At the top, there is a navigation bar with the Apollo logo, the text 'KOMANDNA TABLA' and 'FORUM', and a user profile 'Apollo Farmer' with a notification bell. A language dropdown menu is open, showing options for RS (Serbia), EN (English), GR (Greece), and ES (Spain). The current selection is RS.

Below the navigation bar, the main content area is titled 'Komandna tabla'. It features a 'SHARE' button and a user profile 'AF'. There are four summary cards:

- PARCELE**: 8
- OBAVEŠTENJA O ORANJU (OBRADI ZEMLJIŠTA)**: 0
- OBAVEŠTENJA O NAVODNJAVANJU**: 0
- OBAVEŠTENJA O PROCENI PRINOSA**: 0

A '+ Dodaj Novu Parcelu' button is located to the right of the summary cards.

Below the summary cards is a table with the following data:

Vrste Useva	# Parcela	Hektar Zemljišta	Usluge
Wheat	1	4.00	Tractor, Sprayer, Fertilizer, Harvesting
Maize	5	9.00	Tractor, Sprayer, Fertilizer, Harvesting
Soya	2	2.00	Tractor, Sprayer, Fertilizer, Harvesting

At the bottom of the interface, there is a promotional message: 'VAŠ TRENUTNI PLAN JE SREBRNI' and 'Da li vam treba više? Unapredite svoj plan Apollo Gold daje vam neograničeni broj kupcaca, parcela, vrsta useva i više.' A 'STUPI U KONTAKT' button is located to the right of the message.

HOW TO EDIT PROFILE SETTINGS...

In the dashboard of your **APOLLO** account, click on your name

In the dropdown menu, click on View Profile

Edit your profile settings

To change the language of **APOLLO** platform chose the preferred language from the list

The screenshot shows the APOLLO user interface. At the top, there is a navigation bar with the APOLLO logo, 'DASHBOARD', and 'FORUM' links. A search bar and a user profile dropdown labeled 'Apollo Farmer' are also present. Below the navigation bar, the user's name 'Apollo Farmer' is displayed, followed by a menu with options: 'PROFILE', 'PASSWORD', 'NOTIFICATIONS', 'BILLING', and 'MANAGE YOUR ACCOUNT'. The 'Profile' section is highlighted and contains the following fields:

- FIRST NAME:** Apollo
- LAST NAME:** Farmer
- COUNTRY:** (dropdown menu)
- PHONE NUMBER:** 123456789
- E-MAIL:** farmerapollo@gmail.com
- PREFERRED LANGUAGE:** A dropdown menu with options: English, English, Greek (highlighted in blue), Serbian, and Spanish.

On the right side of the profile section, there is a 'PROFILE PICTURE' area with a 'Click to select image' prompt and a green 'UPLOAD' button.

Insert your phone number in order to receive notification by SMS

The screenshot shows the Apollo profile settings page. The browser address bar displays 'apollo.draxis.gr/settings/profile'. The page header includes the Apollo logo, 'DASHBOARD', a search bar, and the user name 'Apollo Farmer'. The profile form contains the following fields:

- LAST NAME:** A text input field containing 'Farmer'.
- PHONE NUMBER:** A text input field containing 'your phone number'. A dropdown menu is open, showing options for 'Greece (0030)', 'Serbia (00381)', and 'Spain (0034)'. A red box highlights the dropdown menu.
- E-MAIL:** A text input field containing 'farmerapollo@gmail.com'.
- PREFERRED LANGUAGE:** A dropdown menu set to 'English'.

There are two green buttons: 'UPLOAD' next to the last name field and 'UPDATE PROFILE' at the bottom of the form.

When you finish editing, click on UPDATE PROFILE

This screenshot shows the same Apollo profile settings page as the previous one, but with the 'UPDATE PROFILE' button highlighted by a red box. The phone number field now contains '123456789' and the country dropdown is set to 'Serbia (00381)'. The 'E-MAIL' field remains 'farmerapollo@gmail.com' and the 'PREFERRED LANGUAGE' is still 'English'.

To change password, click on PASSWORD in the menu

Insert current password, new password and repeat new password

To edit settings for notification, click on NOTIFICATION in the menu

Set the frequency of notification

Set the way in which you would like to receive the notifications from **APOLLO**

Click on UPDATE PROFILE

CÓMO EDITAR LA CONFIGURACIÓN DEL PERFIL...

En la pantalla de control de su cuenta **APOLLO**, haga clic sobre su nombre.

En el menú desplegable, haga click sobre “Ver Perfil” (*View Profile*).

Puede editar la configuración de su perfil añadiendo una imagen.

Para cambiar el idioma de la plataforma **APOLLO** elija el idioma preferido de la lista desplegable de idiomas (*Preferred language*).

The screenshot shows the 'Profile' settings page in the Apollo platform. The user is logged in as 'Farmer Spain'. The page contains several input fields: 'FIRST NAME' (Farmer), 'LAST NAME' (Spain), 'COUNTRY' (Spain (0034)), 'PHONE NUMBER' (your phone number), and 'E-MAIL' (farmerspain@gmail.com). The 'PREFERRED LANGUAGE' dropdown menu is open, showing options: Spanish (highlighted in blue), English, Greek, and Serbian. A red box highlights the 'Spanish' option.

Introduzca su número de teléfono para recibir las notificaciones por SMS.

The screenshot shows the 'Profile' settings page in the Apollo platform. The user is logged in as 'Apollo Farmer'. The page contains several input fields: 'LAST NAME' (Farmer), 'COUNTRY' (Greece (0030)), 'PHONE NUMBER' (your phone number), and 'E-MAIL' (farmerapollo@gmail.com). The 'PREFERRED LANGUAGE' dropdown menu is set to 'English'. A red box highlights the 'PHONE NUMBER' input field.

Cuando usted termine con la edición, guarde los cambios pulsando sobre “ACTUALIZACIÓN DEL PERFIL” (*UPDATE PROFILE*).

Screenshot of the Apollo user profile settings page. The page shows the following fields and options:

- LAST NAME:** Farmer
- COUNTRY:** Serbia (00381)
- PHONE NUMBER:** 123456789
- E-MAIL:** farmerapollo@gmail.com
- PREFERRED LANGUAGE:** English

Buttons: **UPDATE PROFILE** (highlighted with a red box), **UPLOAD**

Para cambiar contraseña, pulse sobre “CONTRASEÑA” en el menú.

Screenshot of the Apollo user password settings page. The page shows the following elements:

- Navigation Menu:** PERFIL, **CONTRASEÑA** (highlighted with a red box), NOTIFICACIONES, FACTURACIÓN, ADMINISTRE SU CUENTA
- Section Header:** Contraseña
- Form Fields:**
 - CONTRASEÑA ACTUAL:** Su anterior contraseña
 - NUEVA CONTRASEÑA:** Su nueva contraseña
 - REPITA LA NUEVA CONTRASEÑA:** Repita su nueva contraseña
- Button:** ACTUALIZAR LA CONTRASEÑA

Inserte su actual contraseña, nueva contraseña y repita la nueva contraseña; guarde los cambios pinchando en “ACTUALIZAR CONTRASEÑA”.

The screenshot shows a web browser window with the URL `apollo.draxis.gr/settings/password`. The page header includes the Apollo logo, navigation links for 'PANEL DE INICIO' and 'FORUM', a search bar, and the user name 'Farmer Spain'. Below the header, a menu contains 'PERFIL', 'CONTRASEÑA', 'NOTIFICACIONES', 'FACTURACIÓN', and 'ADMINISTRE SU CUENTA'. The 'CONTRASEÑA' menu item is highlighted. The main content area is titled 'Contraseña' and contains three input fields: 'CONTRASEÑA ACTUAL' (Su anterior contraseña), 'NUEVA CONTRASEÑA' (Su nueva contraseña), and 'REPITA LA NUEVA CONTRASEÑA' (Repita su nueva contraseña). A green button labeled 'ACTUALIZAR LA CONTRASEÑA' is highlighted with a red box at the bottom of the form.

Para configurar las notificaciones, pulse sobre “NOTIFICACIONES” en el menú.

The screenshot shows a web browser window with the URL `apollo.draxis.gr/settings/notifications`. The page header is identical to the previous screenshot. The 'NOTIFICACIONES' menu item in the navigation bar is highlighted with a red box. The main content area is titled 'Notificaciones' and includes a 'FRECUENCIA' section with radio buttons for 'Desactivado', 'Diario', and 'Semanal'. Below this is a 'CORREO ELECTRÓNICO / SMS' section with checkboxes for 'Correo electrónico' and 'SMS'. A green button labeled 'ACTUALIZAR PERFIL' is located at the bottom of the form.

Ajuste la frecuencia con la que desea recibir las notificaciones.

Ajuste el medio por el cual le gustaría recibir las notificaciones desde **APOLLO**.

Pulse sobre “ACTUALIZAR PERFIL” para guardar los cambios.

The screenshot shows a web browser window with the URL `apollo.draxis.gr/settings/notifications`. The page title is "Notificaciones". Under the heading "FRECUENCIA", there are three radio button options: "Desactivado", "Diario" (which is selected), and "Semanal". Under the heading "CORREO ELECTRÓNICO / SMS", there are two checkbox options: "Correo electrónico" and "SMS". A red text instruction below the checkboxes reads: "Por favor, elija la forma de notificación que prefiere (Correo electrónico y/o SMS)". At the bottom left of the form area, there is a green button labeled "ACTUALIZAR PERFIL" which is highlighted with a red rectangular border.

ΠΩΣ ΝΑ ΕΠΕΞΕΡΓΑΣΤΕΙΤΕ ΤΙΣ ΡΥΘΜΙΣΕΙΣ ΠΡΟΦΙΛ...

Στην ΑΡΧΙΚΗ ΟΘΟΝΗ του λογαριασμού σας **APOLLO**, κάντε κλικ στο όνομά σας

The screenshot displays the APOLLO user profile dashboard. At the top, the APOLLO logo and navigation links 'ΑΡΧΙΚΗ ΟΘΟΝΗ' and 'ΦΟΡΟΥΜ' are visible. The user's name 'ΧΡΗΣΤΗΣ ΑΡΟΛΛΟ' is shown in a dropdown menu. The dashboard features four main metrics cards, each with a '0' value and a corresponding icon: 'ΧΩΡΑΦΙΑ' (Cultivated Area), 'ΕΙΔΟΠΟΙΗΣΕΙΣ ΟΡΓΩΜΑΤΟΣ' (Crop Variety), 'ΕΙΔΟΠΟΙΗΣΕΙΣ ΠΟΤΙΣΜΑΤΟΣ' (Irrigation Variety), and 'ΕΙΔΟΠΟΙΗΣΕΙΣ ΠΡΟΒΛΕΨΗΣ ΣΥΓΚΟΜΙΔΗΣ' (Yield Forecast Variety). Below these cards is a green bar with labels for 'Τύπος Καλλιέργειας', '# Χωραφιών', 'Εκτάρια Περιοχής', and 'Υπηρεσίες'. A notification box at the bottom states 'ΤΟ ΤΡΕΧΟΝ ΠΑΚΕΤΟ ΣΥΝΔΡΟΜΗΣ ΣΑΣ ΕΙΝΑΙ ΑΣΗΜΕΝΟ' (Your current subsidy package is insignificant) and provides instructions to upgrade to 'Apollo Gold' for unlimited plots, cultivated areas, irrigation types, and services. A green 'ΕΠΙΚΟΙΝΩΗΣΤΕ' (Contact Us) button is also present.

Στο αναπτυσσόμενο μενού, κάντε κλικ στο Προφίλ

The screenshot shows the APOLLO user interface. At the top, there is a navigation bar with the APOLLO logo, 'ΑΡΧΙΚΗ ΟΘΟΝΗ', and 'ΦΟΡΟΥΜ'. A user menu is open, showing the user's name 'ΧΡΗΣΤΗΣ ΑΡΟΛΛΟ' and a notification bell. The 'Profile' option is highlighted with a red box. Below the navigation bar, the main dashboard features three cards: 'ΧΩΡΑΦΙΑ' (0), 'ΕΙΔΟΠΟΙΗΣΕΙΣ ΟΡΓΩΜΑΤΟΣ' (0), and 'ΕΙΔΟΠΟΙΗΣΕΙΣ ΠΟΤΙΣΜΑΤΟΣ' (0). A green bar below these cards contains filters: 'Τύπος Καλλιέργειας', '# Χωραφιών', 'Εκτάρια Περιοχής', and 'Υπηρεσίες'. A central message box states: 'ΤΟ ΤΡΕΧΟΝ ΠΑΚΕΤΟ ΣΥΝΔΡΟΜΗΣ ΣΑΣ ΕΙΝΑΙ ΑΣΗΜΕΝΙΟ. Χρειάζεστε περισσότερα; Αναβαθμίστε το πακέτο της συνδρομής σας Apollo Gold για να έχετε απεριόριστο αριθμό πελατών, χωραφιών, τύπων καλλιεργειών και άλλα.' with an 'ΕΠΙΚΟΙΝΩΗΣΤΕ' button. The URL 'apollo.draxis.gr/settings/profile' is visible at the bottom left.

Επεξεργαστείτε τις ρυθμίσεις του προφίλ σας

The screenshot shows the 'Profile' settings page in the APOLLO application. The user is identified as 'ΧΡΗΣΤΗΣ ΑΡΟΛΛΟ'. The page has a navigation bar with 'ΠΡΟΦΙΛ', 'ΚΩΔΙΚΟΣ ΠΡΟΒΑΣΗΣ', 'ΕΙΔΟΠΟΙΗΣΕΙΣ', 'ΤΙΜΟΛΟΓΗΣΗ', and 'ΔΙΑΧΕΙΡΙΣΗ ΛΟΓΑΡΙΑΣΜΟΥ'. The 'Profile' section contains several input fields: 'Όνομα' (ΧΡΗΣΤΗΣ), 'Επώνυμο' (ΑΡΟΛΛΟ), 'Χώρα' (dropdown), 'Τηλέφωνο' (το τηλέφωνο σας), and 'Email' (το email σας). On the right, there is a 'Φωτογραφία Προφίλ' section with a placeholder image and the text 'Κέντε κλικ για να επιλέξετε φωτογραφία', and an 'ΑΝΕΒΑΣΤΕ' button.

Για να αλλάξετε τη γλώσσα της πλατφόρμας **APOLLO**, επιλέξτε την προτιμώμενη γλώσσα από τη λίστα

The screenshot shows the APOLLO user profile page. At the top, there is a navigation bar with the APOLLO logo, the text 'ΑΡΧΙΚΗ ΘΕΣΗ ΦΟΡΟΥΜ', and a user profile dropdown menu showing 'ΧΡΗΣΤΗΣ APOLLO'. The main content area contains a profile form with the following fields:

- ΧΡΗΣΤΗΣ**: Text input field containing 'ΧΡΗΣΤΗΣ'.
- ΕΠΩΝΥΜΟ**: Text input field containing 'APOLLO'.
- ΧΩΡΑ**: A dropdown menu currently showing an empty selection.
- ΤΗΛΕΦΩΝΟ**: Text input field containing 'το τηλέφωνο σας'.
- EMAIL**: Text input field containing 'το email σας'.
- ΓΛΩΣΣΑ ΠΡΟΤΙΜΗΣΗΣ**: A dropdown menu with the following options: Ελληνικά, Αγγλικά, **Ελληνικά** (highlighted in blue), Σερβικά, Ισπανικά.

On the right side of the form, there is a green button labeled 'ΑΝΕΒΑΣΤΕ' and a text prompt: 'Κέντε κλικ για να επιλέξετε φωτογραφία'.

Εισάγετε τον αριθμό τηλεφώνου σας για να λαμβάνετε ειδοποίηση μέσω SMS

The screenshot shows the APOLLO user profile page, similar to the previous one. The 'ΧΩΡΑ' dropdown menu is now open, showing the following options: Greece (0030), Serbia (00381), and Spain (0034). The 'Ελληνικά' option is still selected in the 'ΓΛΩΣΣΑ ΠΡΟΤΙΜΗΣΗΣ' dropdown. The 'ΑΝΕΒΑΣΤΕ' button is still present on the right. The 'EMAIL' field now contains 'το email σας'.

Όταν ολοκληρώσετε την επεξεργασία, κάντε κλικ στο **ΑΝΑΝΕΩΣΗ ΠΡΟΦΙΛ**

APOLLO ΑΡΧΙΚΗ ΟΘΟΝΗ ΦΟΡΟΥΜ

ΧΡΗΣΤΗΣ

ΕΠΩΝΥΜΟ

ΑΡΟΛΛΟ

ΧΩΡΑ

ΤΗΛΕΦΩΝΟ

το τηλέφωνο σας

EMAIL

το email σας

ΓΛΩΣΣΑ ΠΡΟΤΙΜΗΣΗΣ

Ελληνικά

ΑΝΕΒΑΣΤΕ

Κέντε κλικ για να επιλέξετε φωτογραφία

ΑΝΑΝΕΩΣΗ ΠΡΟΦΙΛ

Για να αλλάξετε τον κωδικό πρόσβασης, κάντε κλικ στο **ΚΩΔΙΚΟΣ ΠΡΟΣΒΑΣΗΣ** στο μενού

APOLLO ΑΡΧΙΚΗ ΟΘΟΝΗ ΦΟΡΟΥΜ

ΧΡΗΣΤΗΣ ΑΡΟΛΛΟ

ΠΡΟΦΙΛ ΚΩΔΙΚΟΣ ΠΡΟΣΒΑΣΗΣ ΕΙΔΟΠΟΙΗΣΕΙΣ ΤΙΜΟΛΟΓΗΣΗ ΔΙΑΧΕΙΡΙΣΗ ΛΟΓΑΡΙΑΣΜΟΥ

Προφίλ

ΌΝΟΜΑ

ΧΡΗΣΤΗΣ

ΕΠΩΝΥΜΟ

ΑΡΟΛΛΟ

ΧΩΡΑ

ΤΗΛΕΦΩΝΟ

το τηλέφωνο σας

EMAIL

το email σας

ΦΩΤΟΓΡΑΦΙΑ ΠΡΟΦΙΛ

Κέντε κλικ για να επιλέξετε φωτογραφία

ΑΝΕΒΑΣΤΕ

Εισάγετε τον τρέχοντα κωδικό πρόσβασης, τον νέο κωδικό πρόσβασης και επαναλάβετε τον νέο κωδικό πρόσβασης

The screenshot shows the APOLLO user interface. At the top, there is a navigation bar with the APOLLO logo, the text 'ΑΡΧΙΚΗ ΟΘΟΝΗ' and 'ΦΟΡΟΥΜ', a search box, and the user name 'ΧΡΗΣΤΗΣ APOLLO' with a notification bell icon. Below the navigation bar, there are tabs: 'ΠΡΟΦΙΛ', 'ΚΩΔΙΚΟΣ ΠΡΟΣΒΑΣΗΣ', 'ΕΙΔΟΠΟΙΗΣΕΙΣ', 'ΤΙΜΟΛΟΓΗΣΗ', and 'ΔΙΑΧΕΙΡΙΣΗ ΛΟΓΑΡΙΑΣΜΟΥ'. The 'ΚΩΔΙΚΟΣ ΠΡΟΣΒΑΣΗΣ' tab is active. The main content area is titled 'Κωδικός Πρόβασης' and contains three input fields: 'ΤΡΕΧΟΝ ΚΩΔΙΚΟΣ ΠΡΟΣΒΑΣΗΣ' (with placeholder text 'ο παλιός σας κωδικός πρόσβασης'), 'ΝΕΟΣ ΚΩΔΙΚΟΣ ΠΡΟΣΒΑΣΗΣ' (with placeholder text 'ο νέος σας κωδικός πρόσβασης'), and 'ΕΠΑΝΑΛΗΨΗ ΝΕΟΥ ΚΩΔΙΚΟΥ ΠΡΟΣΒΑΣΗΣ' (with placeholder text 'επαναλάβετε τον νέο κωδικό πρόσβασης'). Below these fields is a green button labeled 'ΑΝΑΝΕΩΣΗ ΚΩΔΙΚΟΥ ΠΡΟΣΒΑΣΗΣ'.

Για να επεξεργαστείτε τις ρυθμίσεις για ειδοποίηση, κάντε κλικ στις ΕΙΔΟΠΟΙΗΣΕΙΣ στο μενού

The screenshot shows the APOLLO user interface with the 'ΕΙΔΟΠΟΙΗΣΕΙΣ' menu item highlighted in a red box. The navigation bar and tabs are the same as in the previous screenshot. The 'ΕΙΔΟΠΟΙΗΣΕΙΣ' tab is active, and the main content area is titled 'Κωδικός Πρόβασης'. The input fields and the green button are the same as in the previous screenshot. At the bottom of the page, there is a URL: 'apollo.draxis.gr/settings/notifications'.

Ορίστε τη συχνότητα της ειδοποίησης

APOLLO ΑΡΧΙΚΗ ΟΘΟΝΗ ΦΟΡΟΥΜ

ΧΡΗΣΤΗΣ APOLLO

ΠΡΟΦΙΛ ΚΩΔΙΚΟΣ ΠΡΟΒΑΣΗΣ ΕΙΔΟΠΟΙΗΣΕΙΣ ΤΙΜΟΛΟΓΗΣΗ ΔΙΑΧΕΙΡΙΣΗ ΛΟΓΑΡΙΑΣΜΟΥ

Ειδοποιήσεις

ΣΥΧΝΟΤΗΤΑ

Off

Ημερήσια

Εβδομαδιαία

EMAIL / SMS

Email

APOLLO ΑΡΧΙΚΗ ΟΘΟΝΗ ΦΟΡΟΥΜ

ΧΡΗΣΤΗΣ APOLLO

ΠΡΟΦΙΛ ΚΩΔΙΚΟΣ ΠΡΟΒΑΣΗΣ ΕΙΔΟΠΟΙΗΣΕΙΣ ΤΙΜΟΛΟΓΗΣΗ ΔΙΑΧΕΙΡΙΣΗ ΛΟΓΑΡΙΑΣΜΟΥ

Ειδοποιήσεις

ΣΥΧΝΟΤΗΤΑ

Off

Ημερήσια

Εβδομαδιαία

EMAIL / SMS

Email

Ορίστε τον τρόπο με τον οποίο θέλετε να λαμβάνετε τις ειδοποιήσεις από το **APOLLO**

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 687412.

D6.2: 1st APOLLO Training Material

APOLLO ΑΡΧΙΚΗ ΟΘΟΝΗ ΦΟΡΟΥΜ

ΧΡΗΣΤΗΣ APOLLO

ΣΥΧΝΟΤΗΤΑ

Off

Ημερήσια

Εβδομαδιαία

EMAIL / SMS

Email

SMS

ΑΝΑΝΕΩΣΗ ΠΡΟΦΙΛ

Κάντε κλικ στο ΑΝΑΝΕΩΣΗ ΠΡΟΦΙΛ

APOLLO ΑΡΧΙΚΗ ΟΘΟΝΗ ΦΟΡΟΥΜ

ΧΡΗΣΤΗΣ APOLLO

ΣΥΧΝΟΤΗΤΑ

Off

Ημερήσια

Εβδομαδιαία

EMAIL / SMS

Email

SMS

ΑΝΑΝΕΩΣΗ ΠΡΟΦΙΛ

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 687412.

KAKO DA PROMENITE PODEŠAVANJA PROFILA...

Na komandnoj tabli vašeg **APOLLO** naloga, kliknite na vaše ime

U padajućem meniju, kliknite na Profil

Promenite vase postavke profila

Da biste promenili jezik **APOLLO** platforme izaberite željeni jezik sa liste

APOLLO DASHBOARD FORUM Apollo Farmer

Apollo Farmer

PROFILE PASSWORD NOTIFICATIONS BILLING MANAGE YOUR ACCOUNT

Profile

FIRST NAME <input type="text" value="Apollo"/>	PROFILE PICTURE Click to select image <input type="button" value="UPLOAD"/>										
LAST NAME <input type="text" value="Farmer"/>											
COUNTRY <input type="text" value=""/>	PHONE NUMBER <input type="text" value="123456789"/>										
E-MAIL <input type="text" value="farmerapollo@gmail.com"/>											
PREFERRED LANGUAGE <table border="1"><tr><td>English</td><td>▼</td></tr><tr><td>English</td><td></td></tr><tr><td>Greek</td><td></td></tr><tr><td>Serbian</td><td></td></tr><tr><td>Spanish</td><td></td></tr></table>		English	▼	English		Greek		Serbian		Spanish	
English	▼										
English											
Greek											
Serbian											
Spanish											

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 687412.

Unesite vaš broj telefona da biste primili obaveštenje putem SMSa

The screenshot shows the 'Apollo Farmer' profile settings page. The 'LAST NAME' field contains 'Farmer'. The 'COUNTRY' dropdown menu is open, showing options for Greece (0030), Serbia (00381), and Spain (0034). The 'PHONE NUMBER' field contains 'your phone number'. The 'PREFERRED LANGUAGE' dropdown menu is set to 'English'. There is an 'UPDATE PROFILE' button at the bottom and an 'UPLOAD' button at the top right.

Kada ste završili sa menjanem, kliknite na UNAPREDI PROFIL

The screenshot shows the same 'Apollo Farmer' profile settings page. The 'COUNTRY' dropdown menu is now set to 'Serbia (00381)'. The 'PHONE NUMBER' field contains '123456789'. The 'E-MAIL' field contains 'farmerapollo@gmail.com'. The 'PREFERRED LANGUAGE' dropdown menu is still set to 'English'. The 'UPDATE PROFILE' button at the bottom is highlighted with a red box, and a mouse cursor is pointing at it.

Da biste promenili lozinku, kliknite na LOZINKA u meniju

Unesite trenutnu lozinku, novu lozinku i ponovite novu lozinku

Da biste menjali podešavanja za obaveštenja, kliknite na OBAVEŠTENJA u meniju

Podesite učestalost obaveštenja

Podesite način na koji biste voleli da primete obaveštenja od **APOLLO**

HOW TO ADD YOUR PARCELS TO APOLLO PLATFORM...

In the DASHBOARD of your **APOLLO** account, click on +ADD A NEW PARCEL

Insert the information about the new parcel: name, crop type, irrigation system, sowing and harvesting dates

The screenshot shows a web browser window with the URL apollo.draxis.gr/parcel/create. The page title is "Add a new parcel". The form contains the following fields:

- PARCEL NAME:** A text input field containing "Parcel 1", which is highlighted with a red rectangular box.
- CROP TYPE:** A dropdown menu with "WHEAT" selected.
- IRRIGATION SYSTEM:** A dropdown menu with "IRRIGATION SPRINKLER" selected.
- SOWING DATE:** A date input field containing "10/15/2016".
- HARVESTING DATE:** A date input field containing "07/08/2017".

At the bottom of the form, there is a section labeled "MARK YOUR FIELD LOCATION" which is currently empty.

Go to the map below and zoom in to the area where the parcel is situated

When you identify the parcel on the map, click on Draw a polygon symbol

By clicking over map, draw the parcel's boundaries

D6.2: 1st APOLLO Training Material

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 687412.

Click on the first point to close the polygon

Click on SAVE PARCEL. The new parcel is added to **APOLLO**.

CÓMO AÑADIR TUS PARCELAS A LA PLATAFORMA APOLLO...

En el “PANEL DE INICIO” de su cuenta **APOLLO**, pinche sobre “+AÑADIR NUEVA PARCELA”.

The screenshot displays the APOLLO dashboard interface. At the top, the URL 'apollo.draxis.gr' is visible. The navigation bar includes the APOLLO logo, 'PANEL DE INICIO', and 'FORUM'. A search bar with the text 'BUSCAR' is present. The user's language is set to 'ES' and the region to 'Farmer Spain'. The main content area is titled 'Panel de inicio' and features four cards: '0 PARCELAS', '0 ALERTAS DE LABOREO', '0 ALERTAS DE RIEGO', and '0 ALERTAS DE ESTIMACIÓN DEL RENDIMIENTO'. A red box highlights the '+ Añadir Nueva Parcela' button in the top right corner. Below the cards is a table with columns: 'Tipos De Cultivo', '# De Parcelas', 'Ha De Superficie', and 'Servicios'. At the bottom, a message states 'SU PLAN ACTUAL ES PLATA' and '¿Necesita más? Mejore tu plan Apollo.Gold! le ofrece clientes, parcelas, tipos de cultivo ilimitados y más.' with an 'ESTAR EN CONTACTO' button.

Introduzca la información acerca de la nueva parcela: NOMBRE DE LA PARCELA, TIPO DE CULTIVO, SISTEMA DE RIEGO, FECHA DE SIEMBRA y FECHA DE COSECHA.

The screenshot shows a web browser window with the URL `apollo.draxis.gr/parcel/create`. The page title is "Añadir Nueva Parcela". The form contains the following fields:

- NOMBRE DE LA PARCELA:** A text input field containing "Parcela 1", which is highlighted with a red rectangular border.
- TIPO DE CULTIVO:** A dropdown menu with the placeholder text "ELEGIR UNO..." and a downward arrow.
- SISTEMA DE RIEGO:** A dropdown menu with the placeholder text "ELEGIR UNO..." and a downward arrow.
- FECHA DE SIEMBRA:** A date input field with the placeholder text "dd / mm / aaaa".
- FECHA DE COSECHA:** A date input field with the placeholder text "dd / mm / aaaa".

Vaya al mapa de abajo y amplíe en el área donde está situada la parcela.

Cuando usted identifique la parcela en el mapa, haga clic sobre “DIBUJAR POLÍGONO”.

Haciendo clic sobre el mapa, dibuje los límites de la parcela.

Haga clic sucesivamente en las esquinas de la parcela para dibujar su forma en el mapa.

Pulse sobre el primer punto para cerrar el polígono.

Pulse sobre “GUARDAR PARCELA”. La nueva parcela esta añadida a **APOLLO**.

ΠΩΣ ΝΑ ΠΡΟΣΘΕΣΕΤΕ ΤΑ ΑΓΡΟΤΕΜΑΧΙΑ ΣΑΣ ΣΤΗΝ ΠΛΑΤΦΟΡΜΑ ΤΟΥ ΑΡΟΛΛΟ...

Στην ΑΡΧΙΚΗ ΟΘΟΝΗ του λογαριασμού σας **APOLLO**, κάντε κλικ στο +Εισαγωγή Νέου Χωραφιού

ΑΡΧΙΚΗ ΟΘΟΝΗ ΦΟΡΟΥΜ ΧΡΗΣΤΗΣ APOLLO

Αρχική οθόνη SHARE ΧΑ + Εισαγωγή Νέου Χωραφιού

0 ΧΩΡΑΦΙΑ	0 ΕΙΔΟΠΟΙΗΣΕΙΣ ΟΡΓΩΜΑΤΟΣ	0 ΕΙΔΟΠΟΙΗΣΕΙΣ ΠΟΤΙΣΜΑΤΟΣ	0 ΕΙΔΟΠΟΙΗΣΕΙΣ ΠΡΟΒΛΕΨΗΣ ΣΥΓΚΟΜΙΔΗΣ
Τύπος Καλλιέργειας	# Χωραφιών	Εκτάρια Περιοχής	Υπηρεσίες

ΤΟ ΤΡΕΧΟΝ ΠΑΚΕΤΟ ΣΥΝΔΡΟΜΗΣ ΣΑΣ ΕΙΝΑΙ ΑΣΗΜΕΝΟ
Χρειαζοσθε περισσότερα; Αναβαθμίστε το πακέτο της συνδρομής σας Apollo Gold γγ να έχετε απεριόριστο αριθμό πελατών, χωραφιών, τύπων καλλιέργειών και άλλα.

ΕΠΙΚΟΙΝΩΗΣΤΕ

Εισάγετε τις πληροφορίες σχετικά με το νέο αγροτεμάχιο: όνομα, τύπος καλλιέργειας, σύστημα ποτίσματος, ημερομηνίες σποράς και συγκομιδής

Α P O L L O ΑΡΧΙΚΗ ΘΕΣΗ ΦΘΟΡΥΜ ΧΡΗΣΤΗΣ APOLLO 🔔

Εισαγωγή νέου χωραφιού

ΌΝΟΜΑ ΧΩΡΑΦΙΟΥ

ΤΥΠΟΣ ΚΑΛΙΕΡΓΕΙΑΣ

ΣΥΣΤΗΜΑ ΠΟΤΙΣΜΑΤΟΣ

ΗΜΕΡΟΜΗΝΙΑ ΣΠΟΡΑΣ ΗΜΕΡΟΜΗΝΙΑ ΣΥΓΚΟΜΙΔΗΣ

ΖΩΓΡΑΦΙΣΤΕ ΤΟ ΧΩΡΑΦΙ ΣΑΣ ΣΤΟΝ ΧΑΡΤΙ

Πηγαίνετε στον παρακάτω χάρτη και μεγεθύνετε την περιοχή στην οποία βρίσκεται το αγροτεμάχιο

Όταν εντοπίσετε το αγροτεμάχιο στο χάρτη, κάντε κλικ στο σύμβολο Draw a polygon

Κάνοντας κλικ πάνω από το χάρτη, σχεδιάστε τα όρια του αγροτεμαχίου

D6.2: 1st APOLLO Training Material

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 687412.

Κάντε κλικ στο πρώτο σημείο για να κλείσετε το πολύγωνο

Κάντε κλικ στο ΑΠΟΘΗΚΕΥΣΗ ΧΩΡΑΦΙΟΥ. Το νέο αγροτεμάχιο προστέθηκε στο **APOLLO**

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 687412.

KAKO DA DODATE VAŠE PARCELE NA APOLLO PLATFORMU...

Na KOMANDNOJ TABLI vašeg **APOLLO** naloga, kliknite na + DODAJ NOVU PARCELU

The screenshot shows the Apollo Farmer dashboard. At the top, there is a navigation bar with the Apollo logo, 'KOMANDNA TABLA', and 'FORUM'. On the right, there is a dropdown menu for 'RS', a user profile for 'Apollo Farmer', and a notification bell. Below the navigation bar, the 'Komandna tabla' section is visible. It features a 'SHARE' button and a 'AF' profile icon. A red box highlights the '+ Dodaj Novu Parcelu' button in the top right corner. Below this, there are four summary cards: '8 PARCELE', '0 OBAVEŠTENJA O ORANJU (OBRADI ZEMLJIŠTA)', '0 OBAVEŠTENJA O NAVODNJAVANJU', and '0 OBAVEŠTENJA O PROCENI PRINOSA'. A table below these cards lists crop types: Wheat (1 parcel, 4.00 hectares), Maize (5 parcels, 9.00 hectares), and Soya (2 parcels, 2.00 hectares). Each row includes icons for tractor, plant, percentage, and a chart, along with a dropdown arrow. At the bottom, a message states 'VAŠ TRENUTNI PLAN JE SREBRNI' and 'STUPI U KONTAKT' button is present.

Vrste Useva	# Parcela	Hektar Zemljišta	Usluge
Wheat	1	4.00	Tractor, Plant, %, Chart
Maize	5	9.00	Tractor, Plant, %, Chart
Soya	2	2.00	Tractor, Plant, %, Chart

Unesite informacije o novoj parceli: ime parcele, vrsta useva, sistem navodnjavanja, datume sejanja i žetve (datumi se unose u formatu mesec/dan/godina ili izborom iz kalendara)

A P O L L O KOMANDNA TABLA FORUM RS Apollo Farmer

Dodaj novu parcelu

IME PARCELE
Parcela 111

VRSTA USEVA
MAIZE

SISTEM NAVODNJAVANJA
IRRIGATION SPRINKLER

DATUM SETVE
04/10/2018

DATUM ŽETVE
mm/dd/yyyy

April 2018

Sun	Mon	Tue	Wed	Thu	Fri	Sat
1	2	3	4	5	6	7
8	9	10	11	12	13	14
15	16	17	18	19	20	21
22	23	24	25	26	27	28
29	30	1	2	3	4	5

Idite na mapu ispod i zumirajte oblast gde se parcela nalazi (koristiti opcije + i -) i pretraživač radi grubog lociranja (lupa)

The screenshot displays the APOLLO web application interface. At the top, the logo 'A P O L L O' is followed by navigation links 'KOMANDNA TABLA' and 'FORUM'. On the right, there is a dropdown menu for 'RS' and a user profile 'Apollo Farmer' with a notification bell icon. Below the navigation, the main heading reads 'OBELEŽITE VAŠU PARCELU NA MAPI' (Mark your parcel on the map), followed by the instruction 'Kliknite na uglove da nacrtate oblik parcele na mapi' (Click on the corners to draw the shape of the parcel on the map). The central part of the interface is a satellite map of Ruma, Serbia. A search bar on the left contains the text 'Ruma, Serbia'. To the left of the map are zoom-in (+) and zoom-out (-) buttons. To the right are icons for home, share, and print. At the bottom of the map area, there is a green button labeled 'SAČUVAJ PARCELU' (Save parcel).

Kada identifikujete parcelu na mapi, kliknite na simbol Nacrtaj poligon

Klikom na mapu, nacrtajte granice parcele

D6.2: 1st APOLLO Training Material

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 687412.

Kliknite na prvu tačku da biste zatvorili poligon

Kliknite na SAČUVAJ PARCELU. Nova parcela je dodana na **APOLLO**.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 687412.

Izabrati zemlju u kojoj se parcela nalazi u padajućem meniju.....

This project is co-funded by the European Union

A P O L L O

...i kliknuti SAČUVAJ

Formirana parcela se sada nalazi u spisku parcela u Komandnoj table

APOLLO KOMANDNA TABLA FORUM RS Apollo Farmer

Komandna tabla

SHARE AF + Dodaj Novu Parcelu

9 PARCELE 0 OBAVEŠTENJA O ORANJU (OBRADI ZEMLJIŠTA) 0 OBAVEŠTENJA O NAVODNJAVANJU 0 OBAVEŠTENJA O PROCENI PRINOSA

Vrste Useva	# Parcela	Hektar Zemljišta	Usluge
Maize	6	13.00	

Maize

<input type="checkbox"/>	Kupac	Identifikacija Parcela	Ime Parcela	Ha	Region	Shared	Trenutno Vreme	Usluge
<input type="checkbox"/>	Apollo Farmer	805	Parcela 111	4.00	Serbia			
<input type="checkbox"/>	Apollo Farmer	685	Proba111	3.00	Serbia			
<input type="checkbox"/>	Apollo Farmer	697	Vrba-P2	2.00	Serbia	✓		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Apollo Farmer	699	Vrba-P1	2.00	Serbia	✓		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Apollo Farmer	708	Sarengrad - Plot 2	1.00	Serbia	✓		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Apollo Farmer	707	Sarengrad - Plot 1	1.00	Serbia	✓		

This project is co-funded by the European Union

A P O L L O

A P O L L O

USER GUIDE

Version 2.2 - 10.02.2019.

HOW TO USE APOLLO SERVICES...

List of the agricultural parcels added to your **APOLLO** account is displayed in the **DASHBOARD** of your **APOLLO** account. The parcels are classified by **CROP TYPES**

The screenshot shows the APOLLO dashboard interface. At the top, there is a navigation bar with the APOLLO logo, a search bar, and the user's name 'Nikola Paunovic'. Below this, the dashboard displays four key metrics: 28 PARCELS, 5 TILLAGE ALERTS, 1 IRRIGATION ALERTS, and 0 YIELD ESTIMATION ALERTS. A red box highlights a table of agricultural parcels, which is categorized by crop types. The table has the following data:

CROP TYPES	# OF PARCELS	# OF CUSTOMERS	HA OF AREA	SERVICES
Maize	14	1	26.90	Tillage (2), Irrigation (1), Yield Estimation (0)
Wheat	14	1	47.87	Tillage (3), Irrigation (0), Yield Estimation (0)

Below the table, there is a section titled 'YOUR CURRENT PLAN IS SILVER' with a 'GET IN TOUCH' button. The text below this section reads: 'Need a bigger plan? Apollo Gold gives you unlimited customers, parcels, crop types and more.'

A P O L L O

Click on a CROP TYPE (e.g. Maize) to see all the parcels with the crop type

The screenshot shows the Apollo dashboard with the following data:

- 28 PARCELS
- 5 TILLAGE ALERTS
- 1 IRRIGATION ALERTS
- 0% YIELD ESTIMATION ALERTS

CROP TYPES	# OF PARCELS	# OF CUSTOMERS	HA OF AREA	SERVICES
Maize	14	1	26.90	Tractor 2, Planting 1, % Yield, Map, Down Arrow
Wheat	14	1	47.87	Tractor 3, Planting 1, % Yield, Map, Down Arrow

YOUR CURRENT PLAN IS SILVER
Need a bigger plan? Apollo Gold gives you unlimited customers, parcels, crop types and more. [GET IN TOUCH](#)

The screenshot shows the detailed view for Maize with the following data:

CROP TYPES	# OF PARCELS	# OF CUSTOMERS	HA OF AREA	SERVICES
Maize	14	1	26.90	Tractor 2, Planting 1, % Yield, Map, Up Arrow

Maize

CUSTOMER	PARCEL ID	PARCEL NAME	HA	REGION	CURRENT CLIMATE	SERVICES
Nikola Paunovic	411	2_Ilja	3.29	Serbia	sunny	Tractor 1, Planting 1, % Yield, Map
Nikola Paunovic	412	3_Duzine	2.65	Serbia	sunny	Tractor 1, Planting 1, % Yield, Map

Click on the icon of the Tillage service for a parcel on the list

Tillage scheduling service for the chosen parcel is open and ready to use. In the upper part of the window, current weather and weather forecast for the next 6 days is displayed

In the lower part of the window, soil workability map is presented and a graph of timely change of temperature for a selected day

In the dropdown menu, select Soil Moisture option to display the data on the map.

Soil Moisture map is displayed

This project is co-funded by the European Union

A P O L L O

Switch to **Irrigation scheduling service** by clicking on the IRRIGATION tab in the services menu

By default, Irrigation Decision map is displayed.

The map shows one of the two possible information, namely Needs water or Does not need water

In the dropdown menu, select Irrigation dose to see precise amount of water needed.

The Irrigation dose is displayed on the map

In the dropdown menu, select Soil Moisture to get more information on the soil moisture in the rootzone.

FC-field capacity, PWP – permanent wilting point

Switch to Crop Growth Monitoring service by clicking on the CROP GROWTH MONITORING tab in the services menu

The screenshot shows the Apollo web interface for a crop profile named '3_Duzine'. The user is logged in as 'Nikola Paunovic'. The main content area displays several key metrics:

- IRRIGATION SYSTEM:** Irrigation sprinkler
- SOWING:** 2017-04-06
- HARVESTING:** No date set
- YIELD ESTIMATION:** 0 kg/ha

At the bottom, there is a navigation bar with tabs for 'TILLAGE', 'IRRIGATION', 'CROP GROWTH MONITORING' (which is highlighted with a red box), and 'YIELD ESTIMATION'. Below the navigation bar, the text 'Serbia - WEEK 43 - October 22nd' is visible.

NDVI map is displayed by default.

This project is co-funded by the European Union

If you pick on the field, historical data for the location will be present in the graph below

This project is co-funded by the European Union

A P O L L O

By choosing a date in the calendar, the map will be changed to display a vegetation parameter (NDVI, biomass, Chl index) for that particular date.

The screenshot shows the APOLLO dashboard interface. At the top, there is a navigation bar with the APOLLO logo, 'DASHBOARD', and 'FORUM' links, along with a search bar and a user profile for 'Apollo Farmer'. Below this, a summary section displays key metrics: 'Irrigation System' (Center pivot irrigation, Shared, Apollistas User), 'SOWING' (2018-04-10), 'HARVESTING' (2018-09-15), and 'YIELD ESTIMATION' (34.92 Metric Ton). A main navigation bar includes 'TILLAGE', 'IRRIGATION', 'CROP GROWTH MONITORING', and 'YIELD ESTIMATION'. The main content area shows 'Serbia - WEEK 21 - May 23rd' with a date picker set to '2018-05-23'. A dropdown menu is open, showing a calendar for May 2018 with the 23rd selected. Below the calendar, a button says 'SELECT A LAYER FROM THE DROPDOWN LIST'. The map area shows a satellite image of a field with a green overlay. A legend for NDVI is visible in the bottom right corner of the map area, with values: 0.00 - 0.10 (dark brown), 0.10 - 0.20 (light brown), and 0.20 - 0.30 (green).

In the dropdown menu, chose another parameter (LAI, Chlorophyll index, biomass) to display.

The selected parameter is displayed on the map

This project is co-funded by the European Union

A P O L L O

Switch to Yield Estimation service by clicking on the YIELD ESTIMATION tab in the services menu.

The screenshot displays the APOLLO web application interface. At the top, the navigation bar includes the APOLLO logo, 'DASHBOARD', and 'FORUM' links. A search bar and user profile 'Apollistas User' are also visible. The main content area is titled '2_Ilja' and shows 'Maize - Seed type - Parcel'. A 'Loam' icon is present in the top right. Below this, a summary card displays: 'Irrigation System: Irrigation sprinkler', 'SOWING: 2017-04-06', 'HARVESTING: No date set', and 'YIELD ESTIMATION: 12.85 Metric Ton'. A horizontal menu below the card has tabs for 'TILLAGE', 'IRRIGATION', 'CROP GROWTH MONITORING', 'YIELD ESTIMATION', and a highlighted 'YIELD ESTIMATION' tab. The main view shows 'Serbia - WEEK 21 - May 23rd' with a date selector set to '2017-08-01'. A dropdown menu is set to 'Crop Yield'. At the bottom, an aerial satellite image of a field is shown with a 'Click over your field' tooltip.

Yield estimation for the entire field is displayed in Metric Tons. The variations of the yield within the field are presented on the crop yield map, which is displayed by default.

Historical data for yield estimation can be displayed by choosing a date in the calendar.

This project is co-funded by the European Union

Serbia - WEEK 21 - May 23rd

2017-08-01

SELECT A LAYER FROM THE DROPDOWN LIST

Calculated Date: 2017-08-01 00:00:00
Calculated Value: 356.290 g/m2

Crop Yield (g / m²)

- 0.00 - 336.12
- 336.12 - 672.24
- 672.24 - 1008.35
- 1008.35 - 1344.47
- 1344.47 - 1680.59
- 1680.59 - 2016.71
- 2016.71 - 2352.83
- 2352.83 - 2688.94
- 2688.94 - 3025.06
- > 3025.06

In the dropdown menu, chose Crop Residues to display *the map of residues*

CÓMO USAR LOS SERVICIOS APOLLO...

La lista de parcelas agrícolas añadidas en su cuenta **APOLLO** se visualiza en el “PANEL DE INICIO” de su cuenta **APOLLO**. Las parcelas están clasificadas por TIPO DE CULTIVO.

The screenshot shows the Apollo dashboard interface. At the top, there's a navigation bar with 'A P O L L O', 'PANEL DE INICIO', and 'FORUM'. Below this, there are four summary cards: '13 PARCELAS', '0 ALERTAS DE LABOREO', '0 ALERTAS DE RIEGO', and '0 ALERTAS DE ESTIMACIÓN DEL RENDIMIENTO'. A table below these cards lists the types of crops and their associated data. The table has four columns: 'Tipos De Cultivo', '# De Parcelas', 'Ha De Superficie', and 'Servicios'. The 'Maize' row is highlighted with a red border. Below the table, there's a section for 'SU PLAN ACTUAL ES PLATA' with a 'ESTAR EN CONTACTO' button.

Tipos De Cultivo	# De Parcelas	Ha De Superficie	Servicios
Maize	11	558.00	[Icons: Tractor, Plant, %, Bar Chart]
Chinese Garlic	2	6.00	[Icons: Tractor, Plant, %, Bar Chart]

Pulse sobre un “TIPO DE CULTIVO” (p.ej. Maíz) para ver todas las parcelas con ese tipo de cultivo.

Aparecerá un desplegable con todas las parcelas de ese cultivo.

Pulse sobre el icono de servicio de Laboreo en una de las parcelas de la lista.

The screenshot shows the Apollo web application interface. At the top, there's a navigation bar with 'A P O L L O', 'PANEL DE INICIO', and 'FORUM'. Below that, a summary section shows '13 PARCELAS', '0 ALERTAS DE LABOREO', '0 ALERTAS DE RIEGO', and '0 ALERTAS DE ESTIMACIÓN DEL RENDIMIENTO'. A table lists parcels with columns: Tipos De Cultivo, # De Parcelas, Ha De Superficie, and Servicios. The first row is for 'Maize' with 11 parcels and 558.00 Ha. Below this, a detailed table lists individual parcels with columns: Cliente, ID Parcela, Nombre De La Parcela, Ha, Región, Shared, Clima Actual, and Servicios. The 'Servicios' column for the first parcel (Farmer Spain, ID 725, AN_Maize_AIS) has a red box around the 'Laboreo' icon (a tractor).

Tipos De Cultivo	# De Parcelas	Ha De Superficie	Servicios
Maize	11	558.00	[Tractor, Plant, %]

Maize	Cliente	ID Parcela	Nombre De La Parcela	Ha	Región	Shared	Clima Actual	Servicios
<input type="checkbox"/>	Farmer Spain	725	AN_Maize_AIS	1.00	Spain		[Cloud]	[Tractor] [Plant] [%]
<input type="checkbox"/>	Farmer Spain	722	Pozorrubielos	33.00	Spain		[Cloud]	[Tractor] [Plant] [%]
<input type="checkbox"/>	Farmer Spain	728	OR_Matorral_maize	60.00	Spain		[Cloud]	[Tractor] [Plant] [%]
<input type="checkbox"/>	Farmer Spain	730	OR_PC_maize	75.00	Spain		[Cloud]	[Tractor] [Plant] [%]

El servicio de plan de laboreo para la parcela escogida estará abierto y listo para usar. En la parte superior de la ventana, se verá el tiempo actual y la previsión del tiempo para los 6 días siguientes.

The screenshot shows the 'Laboreo' service page for a specific parcel. The URL is 'apollo.draxis.gr/parcel/725/tillage'. The page displays the following information:

- Sistema de Riego: Irrigation sprinkler
- SIEMBRA: 2018-04-07
- COSECHA: 2018-11-30
- ESTIMACIÓN DEL RENDIMIENTO: Metric Ton

Below this, there are tabs for 'LABOREO', 'RIEGO', 'SEGUIMIENTO DEL CRECIMIENTO DEL CULTIVO', and 'ESTIMACIÓN DEL RENDIMIENTO'. The 'LABOREO' tab is active. The page shows the location 'Spain - SEMANA 23 - June 6th' and a 7-day weather forecast:

Wed	Thu	Fri	Sat	Sun	Mon	Tue
[Cloud]	[Sun]	[Cloud]	[Sun]	[Sun]	[Cloud]	[Cloud]
19°C	25°C	27°C	23°C	26°C	27°C	28°C
BAD CONDITIONS						
3 m/s	2 m/s	2 m/s	3 m/s	1 m/s	2 m/s	3 m/s

En la parte inferior de la ventana, se presenta el mapa de condiciones de laboreo del suelo (*SoilWorkabilityMap*) y un gráfico con la variación de la temperatura para el día seleccionado.

En el menú desplegable, seleccione la opción “HUMEDAD DEL SUELO” (*SoilMoisture*) para ver la información sobre el mapa.

Se mostrará el mapa de Humedad del Suelo

This project is co-funded by the European Union

Cambia al Servicio de Riego pulsando sobre la pestaña “RIEGO” en el menú servicios.

This project is co-funded by the European Union

A P O L L O

AN_Maize_AIS

Maize - Tipo de Siembra - Parcela

Sistema de Riego: Irrigation sprinkler

SIEMBRA: 2018-04-07

COSECHA: 2018-11-30

ESTIMACIÓN DEL RENDIMIENTO: Metric Ton

LABOREO | **RIEGO** | SEGUIMIENTO DEL CRECIMIENTO DEL CULTIVO | ESTIMACIÓN DEL RENDIMIENTO

Spain - SEMANA 23 - June 6th

Spain - SEMANA 23 - June 6th

Day	Temp	Weather	Wind	Water Status
Wed	19°C	Cloudy	3 m/s	DOES NOT NEED WATER
Thu	25°C	Sunny	2 m/s	DOES NOT NEED WATER
Fri	27°C	Cloudy	2 m/s	DOES NOT NEED WATER
Sat	23°C	Sunny	3 m/s	DOES NOT NEED WATER
Sun	26°C	Sunny	1 m/s	DOES NOT NEED WATER
Mon	27°C	Cloudy	2 m/s	DOES NOT NEED WATER
Tue	28°C	Cloudy	3 m/s	DOES NOT NEED WATER

2018-06-06

Por defecto, se visualiza el mapa de decisión de Riego (*IrrigationDecision*).

El mapa muestra una leyenda con las dos posibles informaciones, “Necesita agua”(Needswater) o “No necesita agua” (*Doesnotneedswater*).

En el menú desplegable, seleccione “DOSIS DE RIEGO”(IrrigationDose) para ver la cantidad precisa de agua necesaria.

La dosis de Riego se verá en el mapa.

En el menú desplegable, seleccione “HUMEDAD DEL SUELO” (SoilMoisture) para obtener la humedad del suelo en la zona de la raíz.

This project is co-funded by the European Union

A P O L L O

FC (Field Capacity) → Capacidad de Campo.

PWP (Permanent Wilting Point) → Punto de Marchitez Permanente.

This project is co-funded by the European Union

Cambie al servicio Seguimiento del Crecimiento del Cultivo pulsando sobre la pestaña “SEGUIMIENTO DEL CRECIMIENTO DEL CULTIVO” en el menú de servicios.

El mapa NDVI (Índice de Vegetación) será mostrado por defecto.

Seleccionando un punto en la parcela, la información histórica para esta localización se presentará en el gráfico inferior.

Si elegimos una fecha en el calendario, el mapa cambiará mostrando un parámetro de vegetación (NDVI, biomasa, índice de clorofila) para esa fecha particular.

The screenshot shows the Apollo web application interface. The main content area displays a dashboard for the crop 'CM_P4_maize_CO'. Key information includes the irrigation system (Center pivot irrigation), sowing date (2018-04-23), harvest date (2018-11-30), and yield estimation (Metric Ton). A calendar widget is present, showing the date 2017-05-14. A dropdown menu is open, displaying a list of parameters: NDVI, LAI, Biomass, and Cl-Index. The 'Biomass' option is highlighted in blue.

En el menú desplegable, elija otro parámetro para mostrar (NDVI, LAI, Índice de Clorofila, Biomasa).

El parámetro seleccionado se mostrará en el mapa.

Cambie al servicio [Estimación de Rendimiento de Cultivos](#) pulsando sobre la pestaña “ESTIMACIÓN DE RENDIMIENTO” en el menú de servicios.

This project is co-funded by the European Union

A P O L L O

La estimación del rendimiento para la parcela se muestra en toneladas. Las variaciones de la estimación dentro de la parcelase presentan en el mapa de rendimiento del cultivo, el cual se muestra por defecto.

This project is co-funded by the European Union

Se pueden mostrar los datos históricos para estimar el rendimiento eligiendo un día en el calendario.

En el menú desplegable, elija “RESIDUOS EN CULTIVO” para mostrar el mapa de residuos.

ΠΩΣ ΝΑ ΧΡΗΣΙΜΟΠΟΙΗΣΕΤΕ ΤΙΣ ΥΠΗΡΕΣΙΕΣ APOLLO...

Ο κατάλογος των γεωργικών αγροτεμαχίων που έχουν προστεθεί στο λογαριασμό σας **APOLLO** εμφανίζεται στην **ΑΡΧΙΚΗ ΟΘΟΝΗ** του λογαριασμού σας **APOLLO**. Τα αγροτεμάχια ταξινομούνται σύμφωνα με τους τύπους φυτών

The screenshot displays the APOLLO user interface. At the top, there is a navigation bar with the APOLLO logo, the text 'ΑΡΧΙΚΗ ΟΘΟΝΗ' (Main Screen), and 'ΦΟΡΟΥΜ' (Forum). A user profile dropdown shows 'Ioannou Ioannou' and a notification bell icon. Below the navigation bar, the main dashboard features four summary cards: '6 ΧΩΡΑΦΙΑ' (Plots), '0 ΕΙΔΟΠΟΙΗΣΕΙΣ ΟΡΓΩΜΑΤΟΣ' (Fertilization treatments), '0 ΕΙΔΟΠΟΙΗΣΕΙΣ ΠΟΤΙΣΜΑΤΟΣ' (Irrigation treatments), and '0 ΕΙΔΟΠΟΙΗΣΕΙΣ ΠΡΟΒΛΕΨΗΣ ΣΥΓΚΟΜΙΔΗΣ' (Yield prediction treatments). A '+ Εισαγωγή Νέου Χωραφιού' (Add New Plot) button is located in the top right.

Below the dashboard is a table of agricultural plots:

Τύπος Καλλιέργειας	# Χωραφιών	Εκτάρια Περιοχής	Υπηρεσίες
Cotton	5	5.00	Tractor, Fertilization, Irrigation, Yield Prediction
Wheat	1	0.00	Tractor, Fertilization, Irrigation, Yield Prediction

Below the table, a notification box states: 'ΤΟ ΤΡΕΧΟΝ ΠΑΚΕΤΟ ΣΥΝΔΡΟΜΗΣ ΣΑΣ ΕΙΝΑΙ ΑΣΗΜΕΝΙΟ' (Your current contribution package is insignificant). It includes a call to action: 'Χρειάζεστε περισσότερα; Αναβαθμίστε το πακέτο της συνδρομής σας Apollo Gold για να έχετε απεριόριστο αριθμό πελατών, χωραφιών, τόπων καλλιέργειας και άλλα.' (Need more? Upgrade your subscription package to Apollo Gold to have unlimited number of clients, plots, cultivation sites and more.) and a button labeled 'ΕΠΙΚΟΙΝΩΗΣΤΕ' (Contact Us).

Κάντε κλικ σε ένα τύπο καλλιέργειας (π.χ. Αραβόσιτος) για να δείτε όλα τα αγροτεμάχια με τον τύπο καλλιέργειας

The screenshot shows the Apollo dashboard interface. At the top, there is a navigation bar with the Apollo logo, 'ΑΡΧΙΚΗ ΟΘΟΝΗ', and 'ΦΟΡΟΥΜ'. A user profile dropdown shows 'Ioannou Ioannou'. Below the navigation, there are four summary cards: 'ΧΩΡΑΦΙΑ' (6), 'ΕΙΔΟΠΟΙΗΣΕΙΣ ΟΡΓΩΜΑΤΟΣ' (0), 'ΕΙΔΟΠΟΙΗΣΕΙΣ ΠΟΤΙΣΜΑΤΟΣ' (0), and 'ΕΙΔΟΠΟΙΗΣΕΙΣ ΠΡΟΒΛΕΨΗΣ ΣΥΓΚΟΜΙΔΗΣ' (0%). A '+ Εισαγωγή Νέου Χωραφιού' button is in the top right. Below these cards is a table with columns: 'Τύπος Καλλιέργειας', '# Χωραφιών', 'Εκτάρια Περιοχής', and 'Υπηρεσίες'. The table has two rows: 'Cotton' (5 plots, 5.00 ha) and 'Wheat' (1 plot, 0.00 ha). The 'Wheat' row is highlighted with a red border. Below the table is a message: 'ΤΟ ΤΡΕΧΟΝ ΠΑΚΕΤΟ ΣΥΝΔΡΟΜΗΣ ΣΑΣ ΕΙΝΑΙ ΑΣΗΜΕΝΙΟ' and a green 'ΕΠΙΚΟΙΝΩΗΣΤΕ' button.

This screenshot shows the same dashboard but with the 'Wheat' crop type selected. The table now shows 'Wheat' with 1 plot and 0.00 ha. Below the table, a detailed view for 'Wheat' is shown with a table of plots. The table has columns: 'Πελάτης', 'Αναγνωριστικό Χωραφιού', 'Όνομα Χωραφιού', 'Ha', 'Περιοχή', 'Shared', 'Τρέχουσες Καιρικές Συνθήκες', and 'Υπηρεσίες'. One plot is visible for 'Ioannou Ioannou' with ID '571', name '1_Apollo Wheat', area '0.00', location 'Greece', and a sun icon for weather conditions. The 'Wheat' row in the main table is highlighted in light green. The bottom message and button are also visible.

Κάντε κλικ στο εικονίδιο της υπηρεσίας Οργώματος για ένα αγροτεμάχιο στη λίστα

The screenshot shows the Apollo dashboard for 'ΑΡΧΙΚΗ ΟΘΟΝΗ' (Main Dashboard) for user 'Ioannou Ioannou'. It features four summary cards: ΧΩΡΑΦΙΑ (6), ΕΙΔΟΠΟΙΗΣΕΙΣ ΟΡΓΩΜΑΤΟΣ (0), ΕΙΔΟΠΟΙΗΣΕΙΣ ΠΟΤΙΣΜΑΤΟΣ (0), and ΕΙΔΟΠΟΙΗΣΕΙΣ ΠΡΟΒΛΕΨΗΣ ΣΥΓΚΟΜΙΔΗΣ (% 0). Below these is a table of crops:

Τύπος Καλλιέργειας	# Χωραφιών	Εκτάρια Περιοχής	Υπηρεσίες
Cotton	5	5.00	[Icons: Tractor, Sprinkler, Sun, Graph]
Wheat	1	0.00	[Icons: Tractor, Sprinkler, Sun, Graph]

A detailed view of the 'Wheat' crop is shown below, with a table listing individual plots. The plot 'Ioannou Ioannou' is highlighted, showing 571 plots, '1_Apollo Wheat' name, 0.00 ha, Greece location, and a 'Tρέχουσες Καιρικές Συνθήκες' (Current Weather Conditions) icon (sun) which is highlighted with a red box.

At the bottom, a message reads: 'ΤΟ ΤΡΕΧΟΝ ΠΑΚΕΤΟ ΣΥΝΔΡΟΜΗΣ ΣΑΣ ΕΙΝΑΙ ΑΣΗΜΕΝΟ' (Your current subsidy package is insignificant).

Η υπηρεσία προγραμματισμού χρωματοουργικών εργασιών για το επιλεγμένο αγροτεμάχιο είναι ανοικτή και έτοιμη για χρήση. Στο επάνω μέρος του παραθύρου εμφανίζεται ο τρέχων καιρός και πρόγνωση καιρού για τις επόμενες 6 ημέρες

The screenshot shows the detailed view for '1_Apollo Wheat'. It includes a summary of system status: 'Σύστημα ποτίσματος: Irrigation sprinkler', 'ΣΕ ΚΟΙΝΗ ΧΡΗΣΗ: Apollistas User', 'ΣΠΟΡΑ: 2016-11-28', 'ΣΥΓΚΟΜΙΔΗ: No date set', and 'ΕΚΤΙΜΗΣΗ ΣΥΓΚΟΜΙΔΗΣ: 1.30 Metric Ton'. Below this is a weather forecast section for 'Greece - ΕΒΔΟΜΑΔΑ 23 - June 8th' with a 'Loam' soil type indicator.

ΥΡΓΩΜΑ	ΠΟΤΙΣΜΑ	ΠΑΡΑΚΟΛΟΥΘΗΣΗ ΑΝΑΠΤΥΞΗΣ ΚΑΛΙΕΡΓΕΙΑΣ	ΕΚΤΙΜΗΣΗ ΣΥΓΚΟΜΙΔΗΣ
Greece - ΕΒΔΟΜΑΔΑ 23 - June 8th			
Fri 30°C AVERAGE CONDITIONS 3 m/s	Sat 32°C AVERAGE CONDITIONS 2 m/s	Sun 30°C AVERAGE CONDITIONS 1 m/s	Mon 33°C AVERAGE CONDITIONS 2 m/s
Tue 33°C AVERAGE CONDITIONS 2 m/s	Wed 34°C AVERAGE CONDITIONS 2 m/s	Thu 32°C AVERAGE CONDITIONS 2 m/s	

Στο κάτω μέρος του παραθύρου παρουσιάζεται ο χάρτης επεξεργασίας του εδάφους και ένα γράφημα της έγκαιρης αλλαγής της θερμοκρασίας για μια επιλεγμένη ημέρα

Στο αναπτυσσόμενο μενού, επιλέξτε Επιλογή υγρασίας εδάφους για την εμφάνιση των δεδομένων χάρτη.

Εμφανίζεται ο χάρτης υγρασίας εδάφους

ΑΡΧΙΚΗ ΘΕΣΗ ΦΟΡΟΥΜ

Ioannou Ioannou

ΕΠΙΛΕΞΤΕ ΑΠΟ ΤΗ ΛΙΣΤΑ

Soil Moisture

DASHBOARD FORUM

SEARCH

Apollo Farmer

HISTORICAL DATA

This project is co-funded by the European Union

A P O L L O

This project is co-funded by the European Union

APOLLO

Μεταβείτε στην υπηρεσία Προγραμματισμού άρδευσης κάνοντας κλικ στην καρτέλα ΠΟΤΙΣΜΑ στο μενού υπηρεσιών

The screenshot shows the APOLLO web application interface. At the top, there is a navigation bar with the APOLLO logo, 'ΑΡΧΙΚΗ ΟΘΟΝΗ', and 'ΦΟΡΟΥΜ'. A user profile 'Ioannou Ioannou' is visible in the top right. The main content area is titled '1_Apollo Wheat' and includes a sub-header 'Wheat - Ποικιλία σπόρου - Χωράφι'. Below this, there are several data cards: 'Σύστημα ποτίματος' (Irrigation sprinkler), 'ΣΕ ΚΟΙΝΗ ΧΡΗΣΗ' (Apollistas User), 'ΣΠΟΡΑ' (2016-11-28), 'ΣΥΓΚΟΜΙΔΗ' (No date set), and 'ΕΚΤΙΜΗΣΗ ΣΥΓΚΟΜΙΔΗΣ' (1.30 Metric Ton). A navigation menu below these cards includes 'ΟΡΓΩΜΑ', 'ΠΟΤΙΣΜΑ' (highlighted in red), 'ΠΑΡΑΚΟΛΟΥΘΗΣΗ ΑΝΑΠΤΥΞΗΣ ΚΑΛΛΙΕΡΓΕΙΑΣ', and 'ΕΚΤΙΜΗΣΗ ΣΥΓΚΟΜΙΔΗΣ'. The main content area shows 'Greece - ΕΒΔΟΜΑΔΑ 23 - June 8th' and a weather forecast table for the week of June 8th.

Day	Temp	Weather	Wind	Water Status
Fri	30°C	Sunny	3 m/s	DOES NOT NEED WATER
Sat	32°C	Cloudy	2 m/s	DOES NOT NEED WATER
Sun	30°C	Cloudy	1 m/s	DOES NOT NEED WATER
Mon	33°C	Sunny	2 m/s	DOES NOT NEED WATER
Tue	33°C	Sunny	2 m/s	DOES NOT NEED WATER
Wed	34°C	Cloudy	2 m/s	DOES NOT NEED WATER
Thu	32°C	Cloudy	2 m/s	DOES NOT NEED WATER

At the bottom of the weather forecast, there is a date input field showing '2018-06-08' and a 'ΕΠΙΛΕΞΤΕ ΑΛΙΘ ΤΗ ΛΙΣΤΑ' button.

This project is co-funded by the European Union

Από προεπιλογή, εμφανίζεται ο χάρτης απόφασης άρδευσης.

Ο χάρτης δείχνει μία από τις δύο πιθανές πληροφορίες, δηλαδή το νερό χρειάζεται ή δεν χρειάζεται νερό

Στο αναπτυσσόμενο μενού, επιλέξτε IrrigationDose για να δείτε την ακριβή ποσότητα νερού που απαιτείται.

Η δόση άρδευσης εμφανίζεται στο χάρτη

Στο αναπτυσσόμενο μενού, επιλέξτε **Moisture Soil** για να λάβετε περισσότερες πληροφορίες σχετικά με την υγρασία του εδάφους στη ριζική ζώνη.

This project is co-funded by the European Union

A P O L L O

FC-Υδατοχωρητικότητα, PWP – Σημείο Μόνιμης Μάρανσης

Μεταβείτε στην υπηρεσία παρακολούθησης της ανάπτυξης της καλλιέργειας κάνοντας κλικ στην καρτέλα ΠΑΡΑΚΟΛΟΥΘΗΣΗ ΤΗΣ ΑΝΑΠΤΥΞΗΣ ΚΑΛΛΙΕΡΓΕΙΑΣ στο μενού υπηρεσιών

Ο χάρτης NDVI εμφανίζεται από προεπιλογή.

Εάν επιλέξετε το χωράφι, τα ιστορικά δεδομένα για την τοποθεσία θα εμφανιστούν στο παρακάτω γράφημα

This project is co-funded by the European Union

A P O L L O

Επιλέγοντας μια ημερομηνία στο ημερολόγιο, ο χάρτης θα αλλάξει για να εμφανίσει μια παράμετρο βλάστησης (NDVI, βιομάζα, δείκτης ChI) για τη συγκεκριμένη ημερομηνία.

Στο αναπτυσσόμενο μενού, επιλέξτε άλλη παράμετρο (LAI, δείκτης χλωροφύλλης, βιομάζα) για εμφάνιση.

Η επιλεγμένη παράμετρος εμφανίζεται στο χάρτη

Α P O L L O ΑΡΧΙΚΗ ΟΘΟΝΗ ΦΟΡΟΥΜ

loannou Ioannou

ΕΠΙΛΕΞΤΕ ΑΠΟ ΤΗ ΛΙΣΤΑ

Biomass

Biomass (g / m²)

- 0.00 - 153.00
- 153.00 - 306.00
- 306.00 - 459.00
- 459.00 - 612.00
- 612.00 - 765.00
- 765.00 - 918.00
- 918.00 - 1071.00
- 1071.00 - 1224.00
- 1224.00 - 1377.00

Μεταβείτε στην υπηρεσία Εκτίμηση Απόδοσης κάνοντας κλικ στην καρτέλα ΕΚΤΙΜΗΣΗ ΣΥΓΚΟΜΙΔΗΣ στο μενού υπηρεσιών.

Α P O L L O ΑΡΧΙΚΗ ΟΘΟΝΗ ΦΟΡΟΥΜ

loannou Ioannou

1_Apollo
Wheat

Wheat - Ποικιλία σπόρου - Χωράφι

Loam

Σύστημα ποτίματος Irrigation sprinkler	ΣΕ ΚΟΙΝΗ ΧΡΗΣΗ Apollistas User	ΣΠΟΡΑ 2016-11-28	ΣΥΓΚΟΜΙΔΗ No date set	ΕΚΤΙΜΗΣΗ ΣΥΓΚΟΜΙΔΗΣ 1.30 Metric Ton
---	-----------------------------------	---------------------	--------------------------	--

Ανάκληση κοινής χρήσης

ΟΡΓΑΝΑ ΠΟΤΙΣΜΑ ΠΑΡΑΚΟΛΟΥΘΗΣΗ ΑΝΑΠΤΥΞΗΣ ΚΑΛΛΙΕΡΓΕΙΑΣ ΕΚΤΙΜΗΣΗ ΣΥΓΚΟΜΙΔΗΣ

Greece - ΕΒΔΟΜΑΔΑ 23 - June 8th

2018-06-08

ΕΠΙΛΕΞΤΕ ΑΠΟ ΤΗ ΛΙΣΤΑ

Biomass

apollo.dravis.gr/parcel/571/yield

Η εκτίμηση απόδοσης για ολόκληρο το πεδίο εμφανίζεται σε τόνους. Οι μεταβολές της απόδοσης στο χωράφι παρουσιάζονται στον χάρτη αποδόσεων καλλιεργειών, ο οποίος εμφανίζεται από προεπιλογή.

Τα ιστορικά δεδομένα για την εκτίμηση της απόδοσης μπορούν να εμφανιστούν επιλέγοντας μια ημερομηνία στο ημερολόγιο.

This project is co-funded by the European Union

Στο αναπτυσσόμενο μενού, επιλέξτε τα υπολείμματα καλλιέργειας για να εμφανίσετε το χάρτη υπολειμμάτων

KAKO DA KORISTITE APOLLO USLUGE...

Listapoljoprivrednih parcelakoga je dodatanavaš **APOLLO** nalog je istaknutana **KOMANDNOJ TABLI** vašeg **APOLLO** naloga. Parcelesuklasifikovaneprema **VRSTAMA USEVA**

The screenshot shows the Apollo dashboard interface. At the top, there's a navigation bar with the Apollo logo, a search bar, and the user's name 'Nikola Paunovic'. Below this, a 'Dashboard' section features four key metrics: 28 PARCELS, 5 TILLAGE ALERTS, 1 IRRIGATION ALERTS, and 0 YIELD ESTIMATION ALERTS. A table below these metrics is highlighted with a red box, showing crop types and their associated services.

CROP TYPES	# OF PARCELS	# OF CUSTOMERS	HA OF AREA	SERVICES
Maize	14	1	26.90	Tillage (2), Irrigation (1), Yield Estimation (%)
Wheat	14	1	47.87	Tillage (3), Irrigation, Yield Estimation (%)

Below the table, a message states: 'YOUR CURRENT PLAN IS SILVER. Need a bigger plan? Apollo Gold gives you unlimited customers, parcels, crop types and more.' with a 'GET IN TOUCH' button.

Kliknite na VRSTU USEVA (npr. Kukuruz) da biste videli sve parcele pod tom vrstom useva

Dashboard SHARE NP + ADD A NEW PARCEL

28 PARCELS **5** TILLAGE ALERTS **1** IRRIGATION ALERTS **% 0** YIELD ESTIMATION ALERTS

CROP TYPES	# OF PARCELS	# OF CUSTOMERS	HA OF AREA	SERVICES
Maize	14	1	26.90	2 1 %
Wheat	14	1	47.87	3 %

YOUR CURRENT PLAN IS SILVER
Need a bigger plan? Apollo Gold gives you unlimited customers, parcels, crop types and more. GET IN TOUCH

Dashboard SHARE NP + ADD A NEW PARCEL

28 PARCELS **5** TILLAGE ALERTS **1** IRRIGATION ALERTS **% 0** YIELD ESTIMATION ALERTS

CROP TYPES	# OF PARCELS	# OF CUSTOMERS	HA OF AREA	SERVICES
Maize	14	1	26.90	2 1 %

Maize

CUSTOMER	PARCEL ID	PARCEL NAME	HA	REGION	CURRENT CLIMATE	SERVICES
Nikola Paunovic	411	2_Iljia	3.29	Serbia	sunny	1 %
Nikola Paunovic	412	3_Duzine	2.65	Serbia	sunny	%

Kliknite na ikonu Raspored oranja za parcelu na listi

The screenshot shows the Apollo dashboard with a table of parcels. The table has columns for CROP TYPES, # OF PARCELS, # OF CUSTOMERS, HA OF AREA, and SERVICES. The 'Maize' section is expanded, showing a list of parcels with columns for CUSTOMER, PARCEL ID, PARCEL NAME, HA, REGION, CURRENT CLIMATE, and SERVICES. A red box highlights the 'Raspored oranja' icon (a tractor) for parcel 411.

CROP TYPES	# OF PARCELS	# OF CUSTOMERS	HA OF AREA	SERVICES
Maize	14	1	26.90	

CUSTOMER	PARCEL ID	PARCEL NAME	HA	REGION	CURRENT CLIMATE	SERVICES
Nikola Paunovic	411	2_Ililija	3.29	Serbia	sunny	
Nikola Paunovic	412	3_Duzine	2.65	Serbia	sunny	
Nikola Paunovic	413	4_Zmaj	1.72	Serbia	sunny	
Nikola Paunovic	417	8_Djokic basta	1.76	Serbia	sunny	
Nikola Paunovic	418	9_Jankovic	0.58	Serbia	sunny	
Nikola Paunovic	420	11_Peskana 2	0.79	Serbia	sunny	
Nikola Paunovic	422	13_Lubura	2.51	Serbia	sunny	

Usluga rasporeda oranja za izabranu parcelu je otvorena i spremna za upotrebu. U gornjem delu prozora, trenutna vremenska prognoza i prognoza za narednih 6 dana je istaknuta

The screenshot shows the Apollo dashboard with the tillage service page for parcel 411. The page has a date of 2017-04-06 and a 'No date set' button. The 'TILLAGE' tab is selected, and the page displays a weather forecast for Serbia - WEEK 43 - October 22nd. The forecast shows temperatures and wind speeds for Sun, Mon, Tue, Wed, Thu, Fri, and Sat. A red box highlights the 'TILLAGE' tab.

TILLAGE	IRRIGATION	CROP GROWTH MONITORING	YIELD ESTIMATION
2017-04-06	No date set		

Serbia - WEEK 43 - October 22nd

Sun	Mon	Tue	Wed	Thu	Fri	Sat
24°C	17°C	15°C	16°C	13°C	°C	°C
BAD CONDITIONS	m/s	m/s				
2 m/s	3 m/s	3 m/s	3 m/s	2 m/s		

U donjem delu prozora, mapa obradivosti zemljišta je predstavljena i grafikon vremenskih promena temperature za selektovan dan je predstavljen

U padajućem meniju, izaberite opciju Vlažnost Zemljišta da bi vam se prikazali podaci na mapi.

Prikazana je mapa vlažnosti zemljišta

This project is co-funded by the European Union

A P O L L O

Prebacite se na **Uslugu rasporeda navodnjavanja** klikom na dugme NAVODNJAVANJE u meniju usluga

The screenshot shows the Apollo dashboard for a parcel named '3_Duzine'. The dashboard includes a search bar, user profile 'Nikola Paunovic', and a navigation menu with options: TILLAGE, IRRIGATION (highlighted with a red box), CROP GROWTH MONITORING, and YIELD ESTIMATION. Below the menu, there are sections for 'IRRIGATION SYSTEM' (Irrigation sprinkler), 'SOWING' (2017-04-06), 'HARVESTING' (No date set), and 'YIELD ESTIMATION' (0 kg/ha). The location is identified as 'Serbia - WEEK 43 - October 22nd'.

The screenshot shows the Apollo dashboard with the 'IRRIGATION' menu item selected. The dashboard displays a weather forecast for 'Serbia - WEEK 21 - May 23rd'. The forecast includes temperature, weather icons, and irrigation status for each day from Wednesday to Tuesday.

Day	Temp	Weather	Irrigation Status	Wind
Wed	29°C	Cloudy with rain	DOES NOT NEED WATER	1 m/s
Thu	28°C	Sunny	DOES NOT NEED WATER	2 m/s
Fri	29°C	Sunny	DOES NOT NEED WATER	1 m/s
Sat	31°C	Sunny	DOES NOT NEED WATER	1 m/s
Sun	28°C	Sunny	DOES NOT NEED WATER	2 m/s
Mon	28°C	Sunny	DOES NOT NEED WATER	2 m/s
Tue	28°C	Sunny	DOES NOT NEED WATER	2 m/s

Po inerciji, prikazuje se mapa Irrigation Decision.

Mapa prikazuje jednu od dve moguće informacije, naime Potrebna voda ili Nije potrebna voda.

U padajućem meniju, izaberite Irrigation Dose da biste videli preciznu količinu potrebne vode.

Doza navodnjavanja je prikazana na mapi.

U padajućem meniju, selektujte Soil Moisture da biste dobili više informacija o vlažnosti zemljišta u zoni korena.

FC-poljski kapacitet, PWP – trajna tačka uvenuća

Prebacite se na **Uslugu nadzora rasta useva** klikom na dugme NADZOR RASTA USEVA u meniju usluga

The screenshot shows the Apollo web application interface. The page title is "3_Duzine" and it displays details for "Maize - Seed type - Parcel". The interface includes sections for IRRIGATION SYSTEM, SOWING, HARVESTING, and YIELD ESTIMATION. The "GROWTH MONITORING" button is highlighted with a red box.

IRRIGATION SYSTEM	SOWING	HARVESTING	YIELD ESTIMATION
Irrigation sprinkler	2017-04-06	No date set	0 kg/ha

Buttons: TILLAGE, IRRIGATION, **GROWTH MONITORING**, YIELD ESTIMATION

Location: Serbia - WEEK 43 - October 22nd

NDVI mapa se prikazuje prema inerciji.

This project is co-funded by the European Union

A P O L L O

This project is co-funded by the European Union

Ako odaberete polje, istorijski podaci za lokaciju će se prikazati na grafikonu ispod

This project is co-funded by the European Union

A P O L L O

Odabirom datuma na kalendaru, mapa će se promeniti da prikaže parametar vegetacije (NDVI, biomasa, CI indeks) za određeni datum.

The screenshot shows the APOLLO dashboard interface. At the top, there is a navigation bar with the APOLLO logo, 'DASHBOARD', and 'FORUM' links, along with a search bar and a user profile 'Apollo Farmer'. Below this, a summary section displays 'Irrigation System: Center pivot irrigation', 'SHARED: Apollistas User', 'SOWING: 2018-04-10', 'HARVESTING: 2018-09-15', and 'YIELD ESTIMATION: 34.92 Metric Ton'. A main navigation bar highlights 'YIELD ESTIMATION'. The main content area shows 'Serbia - WEEK 21 - May 23rd' and a date picker set to '2018-05-23'. A map of a field is displayed with a green overlay. A legend for NDVI is shown in the bottom right corner of the map area, with values: 0.00 - 0.10 (dark brown), 0.10 - 0.20 (light brown), and 0.20 - 0.30 (green).

U padajućem meniju, izaberite drugi parametar (LAI, Chlorophyll index, biomass) da se prikaže.

Selektovan parametar je prikazan na mapi

Prebacite na **Uslugu procene prinosa** klikom na dugme PROCENE PRINOSA u meniju usluga.

This project is co-funded by the European Union

A P O L L O

APOLLO DASHBOARD FORUM Apollistas User

2_Ilja

Maize - Seed type - Parcel Loam

Irrigation System Irrigation sprinkler	SOWING 2017-04-06	HARVESTING No date set	YIELD ESTIMATION 12.85 Metric Ton
---	----------------------	---------------------------	--------------------------------------

TILLAGE IRRIGATION CROP GROWTH MONITORING YIELD ESTIMATION

Serbia - WEEK 21 - May 23rd

SELECT A LAYER FROM THE DROPDOWN LIST

Procena prinosa za celo polje je prikazana u Metričkim Tonama. Varijacije prinosa u okviru polja su prikazane na mapi prinosa useva, koja se prikazuje po inerciji.

This project is co-funded by the European Union

APOLLO

Istorijski podaci za procenu prinosa se mogu prikazati odabirom datuma u kalendaru.

This project is co-funded by the European Union

Serbia - WEEK 21 - May 23rd

2017-08-01

SELECT A LAYER FROM THE DROPDOWN LIST

Calculated Date: 2017-08-01 00:00:00
Calculated Value: 356.290 g/m2

AUGUST 2017						
SU	MO	TU	WE	TH	FR	SA
30	31	1	2	3	4	5
6	7	8	9	10	11	12
13	14	15	16	17	18	19
20	21	22	23	24	25	26
27	28	29	30	31	1	2
3	4	5	6	7	8	9

Crop Yield (g / m²)

- 0.00 - 336.12
- 336.12 - 672.24
- 672.24 - 1008.35
- 1008.35 - 1344.47
- 1344.47 - 1680.59
- 1680.59 - 2016.71
- 2016.71 - 2352.83
- 2352.83 - 2688.94
- 2688.94 - 3025.06
- > 3025.06

U padajućem meniju, odaberite Crop residues da bi vam se prikazala mapa ostataka

END OF DOCUMENT

This project is co-funded by
the European Union

A P O L L O